

Shallow Water Waves, Solitary Waves and Ocean Waves

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Abstract

In this paper, we study about properties and natures of water waves. Firstly, types of waves, classification of waves and basic properties of waves are presented. Then, we'll talk about solitary waves and show their beautiful phenomenon by mathematically. We construct asymptotic solutions for multi-soliton solutions, using the inverse scattering transform method. Moreover, we study about three types of waves in the ocean such as wind-driver waves, tides and tsunami with their natures and properties.

Introduction

Water waves have attracted the attention of scientists for many centuries. Although much is now understood, they are a continuing source of fascination, as many aspects of their often complicated nonlinear behaviors remains to be fully elucidated.

Waves move by the transmission of energy by cyclic movement through matter. The medium itself (i.e., water) does not travel. Wave motion is not water flow, but is a flow of energy. Ocean waves are all orbital waves, and are characterized by a circular (orbital) motion. They combine the characteristics of longitudinal and transverse waves.

Types of Waves

Surface Wave: A surface wave travels at the free surface of a fluid, the maximum velocity of the wave and the maximum displacement of fluid particles occur at the free surface of the fluid.

Deep Water: A surface wave is said to be in deep water if its wavelength is much shorter than the local water depth.

Shallow Water: A surface wave is said to be in shallow water if its wavelength is much longer than the local water depth.

Shallow Water Waves: Shallow water waves correspond to the flow at the free surface of a body of shallow water under the force of gravity, or to the flow below a horizontal pressure surface in a fluid.

Shallow Water Waves Equations: Shallow water wave equations are a set of partial differential equations that describe shallow water waves.

Solitary Wave: A solitary wave is a localized gravity wave that maintains its coherence and, hence, its visibility through properties of nonlinear hydrodynamics. Solitary waves have finite amplitude and propagate with constant speed and constant shape.

Soliton: Solitons are solitary waves that have an elastic scattering property: they retain their shape and speed after colliding with each other.

Tsunami: A tsunami is a very long ocean wave caused by an underwater earthquake, a submarine volcanic eruption, or by a landslide.

Wave Dispersion: Wave dispersion in water waves refers to the property that longer waves have lower frequencies and travel faster.

Waves Words

The Crests of the Wave: The crests of the wave is the points of maximum elevation above the free surface.

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The Troughs of the Wave: The troughs of the wave is the point of maximum depression below the free surface.

The Wave Length: The wave length (λ) is the distance between two successive crests or successive troughs.

Wave Amplitude: Wave amplitude (a) is the maximum positive value of the surface elevation above mean level.

Wave Height: Wave height (H) is the vertical change in height between the wave crest and the wave trough. Equal to twice the amplitude.

The Steepness: The Steepness is simply the ratio of height and length (H/L).

Frequency: Frequency (f) is the measurement of the number of peak(or crest) or the number of troughs which pass a fixed point per second.

Period: Period (T) is the time interval between two successive crests or successive troughs passing a fixed point; measured in seconds.

The speed: The speed c of the wave is the quotient of the wavelength over period.

Figure 1. A wave frozen in time

Figure 2. Classification of waves

Basic Properties of Waves (All Waves)

$$\text{The wave frequency } f = \frac{2\pi}{T}$$

$$\text{The wave number } n = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$$

$$\text{Celerity } c = \frac{\lambda}{T} = \frac{f}{n} \text{ (speed of propagation)}$$

Mathematical Description of Wave Motion

$$y = a \sin \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (x - ct) \text{ (or) } y = a \sin (nx - ft)$$

$$\text{Progressive waves on the surface of a canal is } c = \frac{f}{n} = \left(\frac{g}{n} \tanh (nh) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Classification of Waves

Wave classification is based on wavelength (λ) and depth of water (D).

A **deep water wave or short wave** is found where the wavelength (λ) is shorter than twice the water column deep.

Deep water waves, if Depth $D \geq \frac{1}{2} \lambda$ (or) $\lambda < 2D$

A **shallow water wave or long wave** is found where $\lambda > 20D$.

Shallow water waves, if $D \leq \frac{1}{20} \lambda$ (or) $\lambda > 20D$.

Intermediate waves are those that fall between long and short waves.

Intermediate water waves or transitional wave, if $\frac{1}{20} \lambda \leq D \leq \frac{1}{2} \lambda$.

Speed of Water Waves

The wave celerity or speed depends only on the **wave length** λ and on the **water depth D**.

- (i) **In deep water**, the little circles of motions are not affected by the bottom of the ocean, Lake and it turns out that the speed of the wave **only depends on the wavelength**.

In deep water, Wave speed = $1.25 \sqrt{\text{wavelength}}$

- (ii) **In Shallow water**, the bottom interferes with the circling of the deeper water, effectively causing a sort of friction, and slowing down the wave and the speed of the wave **only depends on the depth of the water**.

In Shallow water, Wave speed = $3.13 \sqrt{\text{Depth}}$.

Solitary Waves

We can defined a **soliton** is used to describe any solution of a nonlinear equation or system which

- (i) represents a wave of permanent form,
- (ii) is localized, decaying or becoming constant at infinity; and
- (iii) may interact strongly with other solitons so that after the interaction it retains its form, almost as if the principle of superposition were valid.

Historical Background of Solitary Waves

The solitary wave, or great wave of translation, was first observed by John Scott Russel in 1834, while riding on horse back beside the narrow Union Canal near Edinburgh, Scotland. He found that the relation $c^2 = g(h + a)$, where a is the amplitude of the wave and g is the force due to gravity.

Further investigations were undertaken by Airy (1845), Stokes (1847), Boussinesq (1871) and Rayleigh (1876) in order to understand this phenomenon. Finally, Korteweg and de Vries (1895) developed this theory and derived a nonlinear evolution equation

$$\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \tau} = \frac{c_0 \alpha}{h} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \xi} + \frac{3c_0}{2h} \eta \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \xi} + \frac{c_0 \sigma}{2h} \frac{\partial^3 \eta}{\partial \xi^3}, \text{ where } c_0 = \sqrt{gh}, \sigma = \frac{1}{3} h^3 - \frac{Th}{\rho g}.$$

In 1965 Zabushy and Krushal observed the interaction of solitons and obtained the canonical KdV equation $u_t + vuu_x + \mu u_{xxx} = 0$, where v and μ are positive constants.

Figure 3. A typical interaction of two solitons at succeeding times

Computation of Solitary Wave Solutions by Using Inverse Scattering Transform Method

In this section, we give the sketch of the inverse scattering transform method and the idea is as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Schema of the inverse scattering transform method

The unperturbed Korteweg-de Vries equation

$$u_t + vuu_x + \mu u_{xxx} = 0, \tag{1}$$

whose associated time evolution equation is given by

$$\phi_t = -\left(\frac{v}{3}u - 4\mu\lambda\right)\phi_x + \left(C + \frac{v}{6}u_x\right)\phi, \tag{2}$$

in which C is the constant of integration and the Schrödinger scattering problem is given by

$$\phi_{xx} + \left(\frac{v}{6\mu} u + \lambda(t) \right) \phi = 0, \tag{3}$$

with $\lambda_t = 0$ and the scattering data (at any time t) is given by,

$$R(k;t) = R(k;0)e^{8i\mu k^3 t}, \quad d_n(t) = d_n(0)e^{8\mu\beta_n^3 t}, \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, N), \tag{4}$$

and we assume that $u, u_x \rightarrow 0$ as $|x| \rightarrow \infty$. Here $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_N$ are the positive constants. In addition, from the time evolution equation (2), for the case of the discrete spectrum, if we use the boundary condition $\phi \sim e^{\beta_n x}$ as $x \rightarrow -\infty$ we get $C = 4\mu\beta_n^3$, and for the case of the continuous spectrum, if we use the boundary condition $\phi \sim e^{-ikx}$ as $x \rightarrow -\infty$ we get $C = 4i\mu k^3$.

Jost Functions, Jost Coefficients and Related Equations

We define the Jost function $\phi(k, x; t), \bar{\phi}(k, x; t), \psi(k, x; t), \bar{\psi}(k, x; t)$, to be the solutions of the time-independent Schrödinger equation

$$\psi_{xx} + \left(\frac{v}{6\mu} u + k^2 \right) \psi = 0, \tag{5}$$

where $\psi = \psi(k, x; t)$, satisfying the boundary conditions

$$\phi \sim e^{-ikx}, \quad \bar{\phi} \sim e^{ikx}, \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow -\infty, \quad \psi \sim e^{ikx}, \quad \bar{\psi} \sim e^{-ikx}, \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Then, we have $\phi = a\bar{\psi} + b\psi$, $\bar{\phi} = \bar{b}\bar{\psi} + \bar{a}\psi$, $a\bar{a} - b\bar{b} = 1$, $\psi = a\bar{\phi} - \bar{b}\phi$, $\bar{\psi} = -b\bar{\phi} + \bar{a}\phi$, where the Jost coefficients $a(k; t)$ and $b(k; t)$ are given by

$$a(k; t) = 1 - \frac{iv}{12\mu k} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} u(y, t) \phi(k, y; t) e^{iky} dy,$$

$$b(k, t) = \frac{iv}{12\mu k} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} u(y, t) \phi(k, y; t) e^{-iky} dy,$$

while the Jost function $\phi(k, x; t)$ and $\psi(k, x; t)$ are given by the integral equations

$$\phi(k, x; t) = e^{-ikx} - \frac{v}{6\mu k} \int_{-\infty}^x \sin[k(x-y)] u(y, t) \phi(k, y; t) dy,$$

$$\psi(k, x; t) = e^{ikx} + \frac{v}{6\mu k} \int_x^{+\infty} \sin[k(x-y)] u(y, t) \psi(k, y; t) dy,$$

and the potential $\left(\frac{v}{6\mu} \right) u$ is given by

$$\left(\frac{v}{6\mu} \right) u(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ 2ik(1 - \psi(k, x; t)e^{-ikx}) \right\} \text{ as } |k| \rightarrow \infty, \quad (\text{Im } k > 0).$$

In addition, we have the relation

$$\psi(k, x; t)e^{-ikx} = 1 - \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{id_n(t)\psi_n(x, t)e^{-\beta_n x}}{b_n(t)(k + i\beta_n)} + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{R(\xi; t)\psi(\xi, x; t)e^{i\xi x}}{(\xi + k)} d\xi. \tag{6}$$

Gel'fand-Levitan-Marchenko Integral Equation

Now we can be able to express the solution $u(x,t)$ of the KdV equation (1). Following (Gel'fand and Levitan 1955), the above relation (6) gives the function $u(x,t)$, in term of the Kernel $K(x,x;t)$ is

$$\frac{v}{6\mu} u(x,t) = 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} K(x,x;t), \quad (7)$$

where the kernel $K(x,y;t)$ is the unique solution of the linear integral equation

$$K(x,y;t) + B(x+y,t) + \int_x^{+\infty} K(x,z;t)B(y+z,t)dz = 0, \quad (y > x), \quad (8)$$

and is known as the Gel'fand-Levitan-Marchenko integral equation, and $B(x,t)$ is defined by

$$B(X;t) = \sum_{n=1}^N d_n(t)e^{-\beta_n X} + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} R(k;t)e^{ikX} dk, \quad (9)$$

where

$$d_n(t) = \frac{b_n^2(t)}{c_n(t)}, \quad c_n(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \psi_n^2(x,t)dx, \quad (10)$$

while the reflection coefficient $R(k;t) = \frac{b(k;t)}{a(k;t)}$.

Construction of Solution of the Korteweg-de Vries Equation by the Inverse Scattering Transform Method

By the theory of the inverse-scattering transform (Gel'fand & Levitan, 1955 and Marchenko, 1955), the solution $u(x,t)$ of the KdV equation (1), for any time t is constructed.

- (1) First, calculate the discrete spectrum and the Jost functions for $u(x,0)$.
- (2) Second, use equation (4) to define the spectrum and scattering data for any time t .
- (3) Third, construct function B of (9) to find $K(x,x;t)$ for the GLM equation (8).
- (4) Fourth, use equation (7) to obtain the solution $u(x,t)$ of the KdV equation (1).

1-Soliton, 2-Soliton and N-Soliton Solutions

By using the inverse scattering transform, the 1-soliton solution $u(x,t)$ is given by

$$\frac{v}{6\mu} u(x,t) = 2\beta_1^2 \operatorname{sech}^2(\beta_1\theta) = 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \ln \Delta(x,t),$$

where the expression $\Delta(x,t)$ is given by

$$\Delta(x,t) = 1 + e^{-2\beta_1\theta},$$

in which $\theta = x - 4\mu\beta_1^2 t - x_0$, and x_0 is defined by $d_1(0) = 2\beta_1 e^{2\beta_1 x_0}$

and the 2-soliton solution $u(x,t)$ is given by

$$\frac{v}{6\mu} u(x,t) = 12H^2 \frac{[3 + 4 \cosh(2Hx - 8\mu H^3 t) + \cosh(4Hx - 64\mu H^3 t)]}{[3 \cosh(Hx - 28\mu H^3 t) + \cosh(3Hx - 36\mu H^3 t)]^2} = 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \ln \Delta(x,t),$$

where the expression $\Delta(x,t)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(x, t) &= 2 \left\{ \cosh(3Hx - 36\mu H^3 t) - \sinh(3Hx - 36\mu H^3 t) \right\} \times \\ &\quad \left\{ 3 \cosh(Hx - 28\mu H^3 t) + \cosh(3Hx - 36\mu H^3 t) \right\} \\ &= 1 + 3e^{64\mu H^3 t - 4Hx} + 3e^{8\mu H^3 t - 2Hx} + e^{72\mu H^3 t - 6Hx}, \end{aligned}$$

where H is a positive constant. Similarly, by using the inverse scattering transform, the N-soliton solution $u(x, t)$ is given by

$$\frac{v}{6\mu} u(x, t) = 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \ln \Delta(x, t),$$

where the determinant $\Delta(x, t)$ is given by

$$\Delta(x, t) = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + \frac{D_1 h_1 D_1 h_1}{\beta_1 + \beta_1} & \frac{D_1 h_1 D_2 h_2}{\beta_1 + \beta_2} & \dots & \frac{D_1 h_1 D_N h_N}{\beta_1 + \beta_N} \\ \frac{D_2 h_2 D_1 h_1}{\beta_2 + \beta_1} & 1 + \frac{D_2 h_2 D_2 h_2}{\beta_2 + \beta_2} & \dots & \frac{D_2 h_2 D_N h_N}{\beta_2 + \beta_N} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{D_N h_N D_1 h_1}{\beta_N + \beta_1} & \frac{D_N h_N D_2 h_2}{\beta_N + \beta_2} & \dots & 1 + \frac{D_N h_N D_N h_N}{\beta_N + \beta_N} \end{vmatrix}$$

in which $h_n(x) = e^{-\beta_n x}$, $D_n^2(t) = d_n(t) = d_n(0)e^{8\mu\beta_n^3 t}$, ($D_n > 0$).

Waves in the Ocean

Three Types of Waves

In this paper, we will discuss three types of waves, **wind-driven waves, tides and tsunami.**

When the wind blows on the surface of the ocean it produces ripples, waves and swell. Gravitational forces (mostly from the moon and sun) plus centrifugal forces in the solar system produce tides. Tectonic forces such as earthquakes that cause vertical displacements of the ocean floor, submarine volcanic eruptions, landslides and meteorite impacts on the ocean all cause tsunami.

The typical periods, wavelengths, and forcing mechanisms of the waves in the ocean that we discuss are presented in the following table.

Name	Typical Periods	Wave lengths	Forcing mechanism
Ripples	< 0.2 sec	10^{-2} m	wind on sea surface
Sea	0.2 - 9 sec	130 m	wind on sea surface
Swell	9 - 30 sec	100 s of meters	wind on sea surface
Tsunami	15 minutes – 1 hour	up to hundreds of km	seismic
Tides	Several hours 12.4 hour-24.8hours	Thousands of km	gravitational (mainly sun and moon)

When the wind blowing on the ocean’s surface, wind can generate waves locally, called **sea**, which travel in different directions and at different speeds. Wind can also generate waves that travel from a remote location in the open ocean, called **swell**, which travel in one direction and are more regular than sea waves.

Ripples are the smallest and most irregular undulations produced by wind on the sea surface.

Dispersion Relation

$$c = \frac{f}{n} = \left(\frac{g}{n} \tanh(nh) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad f^2 = gn \tanh(nh)$$

is called the **dispersion relation** because it relates the wave period (or its inverse, frequency f) to the wavelength (or its inverse, wave number n). This relation describes how waves of different periods travel at different speeds and get sorted according to their period.

Deep water waves are dispersive (get sorted) as their speed depends on λ and on their period T .

The shallow water waves are non-dispersive because their speed is independent of λ and T .

Group Speed

The group speed is the speed at which a group of waves travel. This is illustrated by a series of distinct waves that arriving at the beach consecutively. The quantitative motion of group speed c_g is derived from the dispersion relation

In deep waters, $c_g = 0.5c$

In shallow waters, $c_g = c$.

Waves Approaching Shore

As waves approach the shoreline, they slow down. In order to keep their frequency constant, their wavelength also has to decrease (speed = frequency \times wavelength). In addition to that, the front of the wave steepens, the height of the wave increase, and eventually the wave breaks.

Modifications of Wave Experience

Waves experience modifications as they approach the coast. These modifications consist of **refraction, breaking, reflection and diffraction**.

Refraction

Like all waves, water waves will refract. Waves seldom approach the shore at exactly 90 degree angle, so the part that contacts the bottom first is bent or **refracted**.

The orthogonal lines of equal energy are always bent toward shallow water. As waves move into shallow water their phase speed c decreases because c is proportional to the square root of the depth D and the period T remains unchanged. **Refraction** is then the **change of direction** of wave crests associated with the change of speed due to **bathymetry**.

Diffraction

Diffraction is the change of direction of wave crests associated with an obstacle. This is the bending of waves around objects, such as wave energy that moves past barriers into harbors.

Reflection

Reflection is the rebound of energy in the opposite direction to an incident wave due to the presence of an obstacle. Reflection occurs before the incident wave dissipates all its energy.

Figure 5. Refraction and diffraction of a wave Figure 6. Reflection of a wave

Breaking

Theoretically, wave break when their steepness $\frac{H}{\lambda}$ equals $\frac{1}{7}$. In reality, waves are rarely steeper than $\frac{1}{12}$. Waves will break when $\frac{H}{D}$ is approximately 0.8, regardless of the steepness. There are three main types of breaking waves: **spilling breaker**, **plunging breaker**, and **surging breaker** as illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Breaking Waves

Plunging breakers have a curling crest that moves over an air pocket. The curling particles outrun the wave. This usually occurs on moderately steep beach slopes.

Spilling breakers are a more common type of breaker found on more gentle beach slopes. They last longer than plunging breakers because their energy is removed more slowly.

Tides

Tides are the rhythmic rise and fall of sea level at every coast of the world. Tides are generated by the imbalance in the solar system between gravitational forces and centrifugal forces.

The imbalance between centrifugal and gravitational forces on Earth causes tides to have typical periods of 12 hours with wavelength of thousands of kilometers. Then ratio of wavelength λ to water depth D is greater than 250 (i.e., $\frac{\lambda}{D} > 250$) so that $\lambda > 20 D$ and tides are considered long waves.

At certain times during the moon's revolution around the Earth, the direction of its gravitational attraction is aligned with the sun's. During these times the two tide producing bodies act together to create the highest and the lowest tides of the year. These **spring tides** occur every 14-15 days full and new moons.

Figure 8. Forces involved in the formation of a spring tide

When the gravitational pull of the moon and sun are at right angles to each other, the daily tidal variations on the Earth are at their least. These events are called **neap tides** and they occur during the first and last quarter of the moon.

Figure 9. Forces involved in the formation of a neap tide

Types of Tides

There are different types of tides in the world according to the period of the waves that dominate the tides. They are diurnal tides, semidiurnal tides, mixed tides with semidiurnal dominance, mixed tides with diurnal dominance. (Diurnal means daily, and semidiurnal means twice daily).

Diurnal tides only exhibit one high and one low water level per day. In parts of the northern Gulf of Mexico and Southeast Asia, diurnal tides can be seen.

The semidiurnal tides display two high and two tides per day. They are common on the Atlantic Coasts of the United States and Europe. The highs and lows have nearly the same amplitude within the same day but do change from day to day as the sun and the moon go from being aligned to being in quadrature (forming a 90 degree angle).

Mixed tides with semidiurnal dominance also display two highs and two lows per day but they are quite different. Hence, within a day have a higher high water, a lower high water, a lower low water and a higher low water. The tides around west coast of Canada and the United States are of this type.

The mixed tides with diurnal dominance are characterized by displaying a diurnal signal most of the days and a semidiurnal signal in some days, most markedly toward neap tides.

Tsunami

Tsunami in the Japanese language means harbor wave. It is a long wave, a couple of hundred kilometers long, many times produced by a vertical displacement of the ocean bottom. Such vertical displacement of the sea floor, caused by an earthquake, pushes water upward and excites a wave at the surface. This wave then displaces radially in every direction about the initial sea surface bulging.

The use of the term **tidal wave** to refer to tsunami is incorrect. Tidal waves are generated by gravitational forces. Their periods are also completely different. While tidal waves have periods of 12 hours, tsunami has periods of 15 minutes to 1 hour.

Tsunamis behave a long (shallow water) waves even in the deep ocean and can propagate through entire ocean basins. These are very small waves at sea, but very large when they reach land and can cause great damage.

Figure 10. Anatomy of the Tsunami

A typical ocean depth is 4,000 m or 4 km. A very deep part of the ocean is around 10,000m, or 10 km deep. Since the wavelength of the tsunamis is so astronomically large compared to the deep of the ocean, the speed of a tsunami is proportional to the square root of the ocean's depth. Estimating the speed of the 2004 tsunami, using **4000m** as an average depth of the ocean,

$$\text{the speed} = 3.13 \sqrt{4,000} = 198 \text{ m s}^{-1} \approx 200 \text{ m s}^{-1} = 720 \text{ km / hour} .$$

The speed of sound in air is on the order of 340m/s, so this wave was really going fast. The most dangerous and destructive aspect of a tsunami is the persistence of its currents. For a 2m tsunami, which is not very large wave but one of respectable size, the currents resulting from it are approximately 3 m/s. It is quite different to experience a 3 m/s current from a wave with a period of, say, 10 seconds, than a 3 m/s current from a tsunami with a period of 30 minutes. The 10 second wave will have its maximum current in just a couple of seconds, while the tsunamis will produce very strong currents for several minutes and in both phases of the wave (flooding and ebbing).

Conclusion

This paper represents about properties and natures of shallow water waves, solitary waves and ocean waves. The most famous shallow water wave equations are the KdV and Boussinesq equations. The KdV equation has played a pivotal role in the development of the Inverse Scattering Transform and soliton theory. We showed that a soliton may interact with other solitons so that after the interaction it retains its form by mathematically, using the inverse scattering transform method. Moreover, we study about three types of waves in the ocean such as wind-driven waves, tides and tsunami with their natures and properties. By using these obtained relations and processes, can also be solved for the problems of other nonlinear wave equation. And of paramount importance is the prevention of natural disasters, ecological

ravage due to a better understanding of the dynamics of tsunamis, steep waves, strong internal waves, rips, tidal currents, and storm surges. This paper will be the subject of a separate study.

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